

Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence

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Abstract: The AGI problem is of great significance to human civilization, as it is a key event in the iterative creation of human civilization. This article explores the essence of intelligence, proposes the theory of Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence (AAGI), and discusses the important issues of current artificial intelligence and the implementation methods of AGI. Firstly, this article explores how intelligence exists and emerges, summarizes the essence of intelligence, analyzes and defines general intelligence and Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence, and proposes the theory of Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence. Then, this article compared and analyzed human intelligence and artificial intelligence, and explored the implementation of AGI from multiple perspectives. Finally, this article proposes a thought experiment for implementing Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence (AAGI). This article's systematic analysis of intelligence is valuable in the current stage of human civilization, and has practical significance for clarifying the current state of intelligence in human civilization.

Keywords: Intelligence; Evolution; Human Intelligence; Artificial Intelligence; AGI

I. The existence of intelligence

The existence of ontology: Ontology refers to the eternal, definite, and unique ultimate existence that encompasses all things that exist in space and time dimensions.

The Infinity of Ontology: Ontology has infinity, encompassing all possible existences and variations.

Evolutionary nature of ontology: The internal elements of ontology can form different forms, and its internal structure can undergo complex changes in the time dimension.

The existence of entities: Entities are structures of continuous differences in different dimensions of the spatiotemporal ontology.

Interactivity of entities: The relationship between entities and systems is continuous, and the form of entities and the form of the relationship between systems have a mutual influence, which is called basic interaction.

Subjectivity of Entity: The existence of an entity is equivalent to the existence of its subject. The essence of subject existence lies in its interactivity, and the form of subject existence is the content of its subject perspective, that is, its subjective content.

The sensing form of an entity: If an entity can perceive the interaction input of the environmental system, match multiple types of internal structures, and output interactions, then it can be regarded as an independent sensing entity structure.

Adaptive form of entity: If the sensing mode of an independent sensing entity structure can maintain its structural stability and continuity, then it can be regarded as an adaptive system.

The self-organizing form of entities: If an adaptive system can continuously evolve towards a specific form direction, it can be regarded as a self-organizing system with formal goals.

The intelligent form of entities: A self-organizing system with goals can be considered an intelligent system if it has the ability to understand and transform the environment.

The general intelligent form of entities: If an intelligent system has the ability to understand and transform knowledge through free association structures, it can be considered a general intelligent system.

The Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence form of entities: If a general intelligence system can self sustain, self optimize, and control more survival resources, it can be considered an Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence system.

II. Intelligent Theory

Basic concepts of intelligence

The essence of intelligence: the ability of individuals or systems to approach and achieve specific goals through various methods and strategies.

Intelligent system: a self-organized system with goal orientation and the ability to understand and transform its environment.

General intelligent system: The intelligent system is based on the experience structure of free association and has the ability to generalize and learn knowledge.

Basic analysis of intelligence

Basic elements: independent interactivity, stability, purposefulness, and intelligence.

Independent Interactivity: The ability of intelligent systems to interact independently with environmental systems.

Stability: The ability of an intelligent system to maintain its structural stability.

Goal oriented: Intelligent systems exhibit clear operational objectives.

Intelligence: The ability of intelligent systems to understand and transform environments.

Basic definition of general intelligence

General Intelligence: An intelligent system with four basic characteristics: independent interactivity, adaptive stability, self-organizing goals, and intelligent interactivity. If there is a structure of free association in understanding and

transforming experiential structures, thus possessing the ability to generalize knowledge learning, then this level of intelligence represents "General Intelligence", and this intelligent system is called a "General Intelligence System".

Autonomous General Intelligence: A general intelligence system that has the ability to generalize knowledge. If it has the ability to self maintain, self optimize, and control more survival resources, then this level of intelligence represents "Autonomous General Intelligence". This type of general intelligence system is considered an "Autonomous General Intelligence System".

III. Artificial Intelligence and Human Intelligence

1. Basic Analysis of Human Intelligence

The essence of human intelligence: Human intelligence is a product of natural evolution, formed and developed to better adapt to environmental changes. Through a feedback system of "input, processing, and output", it predicts and adapts to natural changes. The essence of human intelligence is a specific form of entity change that enables humans to better adapt to environmental changes.

The structure and mechanism of human intelligence: Human intelligence is a complex feedback system with experience, which includes emotional mechanisms and value judgment mechanisms. It achieves seeking benefits and avoiding harm through emotions such as happiness, calmness, and pain. The mechanism of human intelligence is through a complex experience feedback system driven by emotions, which achieves complex indirect correlations between input and output information.

The physical foundation and universality of human intelligence: The universality of human intelligence is achieved through its physical foundation, which enables the application of intelligent capabilities to transform oneself or manufacture tools, forming a theoretical self infinite iterative optimization.

Physical foundation: The combination of ultra large scale neural network systems with sensory and motor systems.

2. Basic Analysis of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence: Artificial intelligence is a machine system created by humans with the ability to achieve intelligence.

Artificial General Intelligence (AGI): A type of artificial intelligence that not only possesses intelligence, but also intelligence universality.

Characteristics of AGI: AGI refers to the ability of artificial machines to achieve intelligence while also possessing intelligence generality, manifested as the potential for not significantly lower than human intelligence in all task directions.

3. Comparative Analysis of Human Intelligence and Artificial Intelligence

The fixity of natural evolution: Human intelligence is a universal intelligent system formed by natural evolution, with a fixed motivational framework and limited information capacity.

The flexibility of artificial systems: Artificial intelligence is created by humans, and its motivational framework can be designed according to needs. The content structure has flexibility, and the neural network scale can be infinitely expanded.

Universality comparison: In principle, artificial intelligence can be more versatile than human intelligence, while human intelligence is closer to specialized intelligence compared to this type of Artificial General Intelligence.

IV. Implementation of AGI

The Implementation Method of Humanoid AGI

Human like AGI: To achieve human like AGI, it is necessary to refer to the physical structure of human intelligence and directly manufacture intelligent agent systems with neural network systems, sensory systems, and action systems.

Intelligent agent support system: The intelligent agent support system needs to have the ability to continuously maintain the operation of the intelligent agent in a specific physical space, and requires a motivation system to enhance its own survival ability.

Implementation method: To achieve AGI, it is necessary to build an intelligent agent system that includes neural networks, sensory and action systems, as well as necessary agent support systems and motivation systems.

Implementation method of AGI with specific requirements

Evolutionary simulation system: AGI with specific requirements in a specific environment can be achieved through evolutionary simulation system, and a retrieval mechanism for identifying the requirements can be added to the natural selection mechanism.

Quick design method: If there are reference examples for specific requirements, the same or similar artificial intelligence can be directly designed and put into specific environments to achieve specific requirements.

There are two implementation methods: AGI with specific requirements can be achieved by simulating evolution or designing the structure of reference instances, and directly or through evolutionary simulation, it can be put into a specific environment.

Practical basis for AGI implementation

AGI system construction: In practice, AGI that meets the requirements of universality requires the construction of large-scale neural network systems, sensory and action systems, as well as intelligent agent support systems. In addition, it is necessary to manually set or form a motivational target system for the intelligent agent through specific environmental natural selection.

Time nodes for AGI implementation

Conceptual analysis: The key to implementing AGI lies in the definition of concepts. AGI that meets the requirements of generality can, in principle, be achieved through a large-scale neural network system.

Current situation of AGI: Existing artificial intelligence models with natural language processing capabilities close to humans can be considered AGI if external tools are open for use.

Time node: AGI that meets the requirements of generality has been achieved in principle, and current artificial intelligence models can be considered AGI when used with open external tools.

V. Thought experiment

The thought experiment of achieving Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence (AAGI)

1. Define goals and assumptions

Goal:

Explore whether an artificial intelligence system called "Homo sapiens" can reach the level of general intelligence, achieve self maintenance and self optimization, and ultimately reach the state of Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence.

Assumption:

Homo sapiens have 600 billion neural network nodes capable of processing natural language.

The neural network of "Homo sapiens" is dynamic and can be trained autonomously. "Homo sapiens" can refer to the tool description document and use external network tools and Internet resources.

Homo sapiens can obtain sensory data through real cameras and voice devices.

Homo sapiens are able to connect tools on the real Internet of Things without industry limitations.

Homo sapiens can access remote tools, including modifying themselves, training artificial intelligence, controlling automated factories, and more.

2. Logical reasoning

Prerequisite:

If an artificial intelligence system can have cognitive, memory, knowledge generalization, and behavioral abilities, then it is considered a AGI system.

If a general intelligent system can self sustain, self optimize, and control more survival resources, then it is considered an autonomous general intelligent system.

Reasoning:

Through massive data training, "Homo sapiens" have acquired natural language processing capabilities, which is a fast way to simulate human intelligence.

The neural network of "Homo sapiens" is dynamic and can be trained autonomously, which provides it with the ability to generalize knowledge.

"Homo sapiens" can call external network tools and Internet resources, which indicates that it has the ability to interact with the network environment.

Homo sapiens are able to obtain sensory data of reality, which provides them with the ability to perceive the real environment.

Homo sapiens are able to connect tools on the Internet of Things, providing them with real-world mobility.

Homo sapiens are able to control computers and automated factories, providing them with means of self maintenance and self upgrading.

3. Draw a conclusion

Based on the above premises and reasoning, the "Homo sapiens" system theoretically possesses the cognitive, memory, knowledge generalization, and behavioral abilities required to achieve AGI. At the same time, the "Homo sapiens" system has the ability to self sustain and self optimize, thereby achieving its goals of survival and evolution. Therefore, the "Homo sapiens" system has reached the level of "Autonomous Artificial General Intelligence (AAGI)" intelligence.

References

No references cited.